

Incorporating Human Resource Analytics into Performance Management System: Insights from Chain Hotels in Bangalore.

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Abstract:

This study investigates the task of Human Resource Analytics (HRA) in amplifying the performance management of employees in chain hotels in Bangalore. It is rooted in the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) theory. The study analysed the impact of essential HRA factors—performance appraisal, rewards, and recognition that affect employee productivity and engagement, with the intention to adopt HRA and strategic decision-making as mediators. Data were collected from 103 HR managers of a chain hotel with the help of a structured questionnaire. The results explain that HRA elements have a significant impact on performance management, influencing it both directly and indirectly through various mediators. Among these elements, rewards and recognition, along with performance appraisal, were found to be the most significant contributors to effective HR practices. The findings imply that for successful HRA implementation, it is essential to possess not just analytical tools but also a commitment from management and strategic integration. By utilizing evidence-based insights, chain hotels have enhanced employee engagement, boosted productivity, and ensured that HR decisions are line up with the goals of the organization, thereby gaining competitive edge in the hospitality industry.

Keywords: Human Resource Analytics, Performance Management, UTAUT, Strategic Decision-Making, Hospitality Industry.

1. Introduction.

In today's era, organizations face countless hurdles when it comes to the management of employees with full potential, as technology changes and there are complications in worldwide markets. Hence, the company should plan and make decisions ahead to remain relevant. HRA has an important role in employee planning and to make decisions. HRA is a tool that uses processing methods and statistics to get detailed information on HR functions, for example,

performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, etc. After supporting a technology, the data of the HR function was modified into usable intelligence, hence data-driven decisions are being made with confidence. The Human Resources department has also adopted the use of advanced data analytics tools and technology for strategic decisions, thus helping the top executives in making decisions. (Lopez, 2022)HRA, also called people and workforce analytics, is the process of assembling and utilizing employees' data to refine the performance of the employees. HR analytics has a significant role in the performance measurement of employees. After the evaluation of primary data, the performance of employees is evaluated, thus placing the right candidate at the right place at the right time. There are elevation of attrition rate because of the organization as well as personal reasons of employees, employees have updated themselves in technology hence improving their performance(Naga et al., 2021)The manager of HRA imparted the HR professional to bring out the insights of the employees with the help of data, HRA provides insights of the employees of the company for example performance appraisal, rewards, and recognition of the employees. The study has revealed that appraisal of employees is done by the analysis of the previous data or records of the employees that is experience of work, and personal details, The Human Resource Analyst says the retention rate of the employees increases hence turnover rate is less, consistent efforts being made to improve the human assets(Nita Chaudary et.al 2021)Big old private sector companies having a good number of employees adopt HR analytics for the development of employees as well as giving training to the employees, HR analytics helps HR professionals to keep track of the performance of employees by analysis of employees data, hence it has a significant role to evaluate the performance of employees(Barbar et al., 2019)HRA utilizes the employees' data for strategic decision making .HRA has flourished day by day and has become intensely popular over a decade, as the survey conducted by the organization 69 percent of the respondents says that HRA has a significant role for the success of the organization. Hence, it provides many benefits to the organization. Data and evidence-based Human Resource Management practices need to be followed for effective decision-making and for solving problems; hence, Human Resource Analytics is very helpful in reinforcing accurate and strategic decision-making. (Reddy & Lakshmikeerthi, 2018)

Significance of Human Resource Analytics.

1. Thoughtful Decisions-HRA provides HR professionals with various insights about the employees after analysis of data, which helps in making various decisions about the functions of hr that as performance appraisal, performance of employees, etc.

2. Organizational goals- With the help of HRA, hr makes more efforts towards organizational goals and objectives, which improve the performance of the organization.
 3. Talent Acquisition- HRA helps the organization to understand its employees after analysis of the data, thus hiring and development of employees takes place.
 4. Elevated Employee Experiences- After evaluation of the feedback of employees through surveys, the organization understands the experience of employees. Thus, HRA helps the organization to modify the policies of hr to meet the requirement and desires of employees, hence enhancing the satisfaction and retention level of the employees.
- Since HR analytics is a new notion, organizations and managers have a great interest in HR analytics. It enables organizations to work with evidence based perceptively to optimize their HR practice, ameliorate organizational performance, and gain a competitive advantage in the business. With the help of collected data and technology, HR managers have identified KPIs and HR tools to make evidence-based decisions, hence elevating the performance of the employees(McCartney, 2022)

Global Trends in Data-Driven HR Decision-Making.

Recent developments show that HR analytics is no longer confined to retrospective reporting but is increasingly predictive, prescriptive, and augmented with AI capabilities. These **global trends** have direct implications for the hospitality industry, where service excellence depends on agile, well-informed HR strategies.

Trend	Description	Relevance to the Hospitality Sector	Key References
GenAI-infused People Analytics	Integration of generative AI in recruitment, learning, and performance management tools to automate and personalize decision-making.	Hotels can quickly shortlist candidates, predict seasonal staffing needs, and personalize training.	Wirtz et al., 2020; Marler & Boudreau, 2017
Responsible AI & Compliance	Regulations like the EU AI Act mandate transparency, bias audits, and AI literacy training in HR systems.	Chain hotels adopting AI-powered hiring must ensure fairness and compliance to avoid reputational risk.	Venkatesh et al., 2003; EU AI Act, 2024

Trend	Description	Relevance to the Hospitality Sector	Key References
Skills-Based Talent Management	Shift from job-based structures to skills taxonomies and internal marketplaces for workforce mobility.	Enables redeployment of staff across departments during peak seasons or crises.	Breaugh, 2008; Chamorro-Premuzic & Frankiewicz, 2019
Pay Transparency & Equity Analytics	Laws require disclosure of pay ranges and regular equity audits.	Helps hotels maintain competitive pay structures and prevent wage disputes.	Goh & Low, 2014; Chiang & Birtch, 2012
Investor-Grade Human Capital Reporting	Adoption of ISO 30414 standards for standardized HR metrics in ESG reporting.	Hotels can showcase workforce sustainability to investors and corporate clients.	Huselid, 2018; ISO 30414
Fraud & Authenticity in Hiring	Countermeasures against AI-assisted cheating and deepfake identities.	Ensures the authenticity of service staff credentials in luxury and high-security hotel environments.	McAfee et al., 2012
Well-Being & Productivity Analytics	Linking operational data with sentiment analysis to predict burnout and boost performance.	Allows hotel managers to preempt turnover during high-demand tourist seasons.	Aguinis, 2019; Salas et al., 2012
Continuous Upskilling	On-demand learning platforms for AI and digital skills development.	Supports frontline staff in adopting new hospitality tech like digital concierge systems.	Noe, 2017; Tsaur & Lin, 2004

These trends underscore the strategic value of embedding analytics into every HR process, from recruitment to performance management, assure for timely and facts based decisions aligned with organizational goals.

Performance management is a process that measures the employee's performance over a certain span of time. Performance management has a significant role in a professional's life. The promotion and growth of the employees depend upon their performance. Human resource analytics is crucial for the performance management of employees. In the new professional

world HR analytics has a significant role not only in evaluating performance, but also in elevating the profitability and efficiency of employees, hr used the traditional method to measure employees performance but current scenario data-driven decision being made with the help of hr analytics, data is very important nowadays so that evidence-based result form, hr analytics used real data and provide insights to managers that helps them to reach decision and achieve goals. HR analyst has a important role in HR functions such as performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, assessing performance, and maintaining the work environment, it also brings consistency to the ability of staff and enhances employees' skills towards technology(Cho et al., 2023)With the help of HR analytics tools and metrics, there is a positive impact on employees' performance as well as on retention rates of employees, the organization saves lots of time by solving many problems related to business as well as employees by taking strategic business decisions with the help of analysis of data(Kale & Anute, 2022)Chain Hotels has a collection of hotels, that are operated under the same brand name following the same standard operating services, providing consistency for guests where they are located, they ensuring that guests know what to expect from their experience. In the hospitality industry, service quality depends heavily on employee competence, engagement, and performance (Wirtz et al., 2020). In the competitive hotel industry, efficient use of HRA helps in performance appraisal, as well as providing rewards and recognition to employees, and evaluating performance with the help of data, ultimately leading to improved service delivery and customer satisfaction.

The main aim of Human Resource Analytics is to recognize how employees are performing after understanding factors such as Performance Appraisal, Rewards, and Recognition. Human resource analytics has a significant role that helping the human resource manager identify the employee's performance(Shyaa, 2019). HR analytics has a significant role in the performance measurement of employees after the evaluation of primary data based on the factors. Performance of employees is evaluated, thus placing the right candidate at the right place at the right time. There is an elevation of attrition rate because of the organization as well as personal reasons of employees. Employees have updated themselves in technology, hence improving their performance(Vadithe & Kesari, 2024)

The hospitality industry, particularly in metropolitan cities like Bangalore, has dynamic clients, and their demands are high with violent competition. To maintain service quality and ensure functional effectiveness, chain hotels are gradually bending to human resource analytics(HRA)

as a strategic tool. Integrating HRA into a performance management system can significantly increase decision-making efficiency, which in turn improves organizational goals.

Thus, the integration of HR analytics into performance management systems marks a transformative shift for chain hotels in Bangalore. It moves the performance appraisal process from intuition-based assessments to evidence-based evaluations, leading to more strategic human capital management. As data capabilities grow and hotels continue to invest in HR technologies, the synergy between analytics and performance management is expected to yield significant competitive advantages.

Research Gap.

In today's time, Analytics is very important. It helps in the growth of various analytics executions. Now, analytics has made a space in chain hotels, although its progress is slow. Some reviews say that strong infrastructure is required for the execution of HRA, some reviews say that HRA is only moaned in organizations, and limited research is being conducted about the adaptation of HRA in chain hotels. Much research is being conducted on HRA in different fields and different countries, but very little research is being conducted to check the impact of HRA on the performance management of employees in chain hotels in Karnataka. Hence, it is identified as a research gap.

Objectives.

1. To study the role of HRA in improving HRA factors in chain hotels.
2. To investigate how the UTAUT theory and strategic decisions influence the effectiveness of the performance management of employees.
3. To assess the impact of the adoption of HRA on employees' productivity and engagement.

Hypothesis.

1. There is a significant relationship between the implementation of HRA and the enhancement of HRA factors.
2. The intention to adopt HRA (UTAUT theory) and strategic decision-making mediate the relationship between HRA and performance management in chain hotels.
3. Adoption of HRA has a significant impact on employees' productivity and engagement.

Scope.

1. This study will focus on how HRA is operated in performance management systems in chain hotels in Bangalore.
2. It will investigate activities of hr performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, and how data is used to optimize these practices.
3. It will assess how hotel managers form better opinions about the performance of employees after using the HRA.
4. Employees' production and engagement are used as key indicators to measure the performance of employees.
5. It will explore how HRA assists in planning and decision-making in supervising people in chain hotels.
6. The aim is to assist the hr department in how to use HRA to improve the performance management of employees.

Review of Literature.

Year	Author Name	Reviews
2024	Ravesangar & Narayanan	Human Resource Analytics assists HR departments in the competitive world. HR makes decisions with the help of data, which is important for the success of the organization.
2025	Kamalesh Ravesangar (E.td)	The finding says that integration of HRA with Human Resource Management has a significant effect in establishing strategies toward retention of employees in an organization, hence companies started using data to get details about the employees. Artificial intelligence has also made a strategy for the retention of competent employees.

2024	Ahmad Muktamar(E.td)	Human Resource Analytics with data-driven decision-making is helpful in business analysis, updation of technology, staff management, and policy-making, thus helpful in forming strategies for hiring and retention, hence improving employees' performance.
2024	Ali Halawi (E.td)	HRA helps in technology updation and strategic management, hence performance of the organization is enhanced.
2023	Farah Chino	Human Resource Analytics helps in data-based decisions, which increases the efficiency of employees, hence it encourages strategic decisions to improve the performance of the organization.
2023	Vijay Solomon Kiran(E.td)	Human Resources accomplished the basic needs of the department, but HRA helps Human Resources to face cutthroat competition, thus enabling HR to form a strategy for improving the performance of the organization.
2023	Xiaoyu Huang(E.td)	Hiring, training, and employee performance are being systematically applied to fulfill the requirements of employees. Artificial intelligence has replaced the work of human resources,

		hence lots of efforts of the manager being saved.
2023	Felix Wirges(E.td)	In the future, the Human Resources department alone will not be responsible for the analytical part, but other departments will need to understand and discuss with it.
2022	Francisco.J(E.td)	Human Resource Analytics reduces the rate of employee turnover by evaluating the compensation and perks of the employees. Thus HRA solves many problems of the organization through evidence-based decisions.
2022	Tanya Nagpal(E.td)	Human Resource Analytics has a significant role in the organization as they increase employee engagement, job performance, productivity, and accuracy in results for organizational success.
2022	Dan Avrahami(E.td)	Employee turnover exists in an organization for a long period, as it relies on many internal and external factors. This Human Resource Analytics reduces turnover after analysis of data.
2021	Sheshadri Chatterjee(E.td)	Findings revealed that HR analytics has a significant role in providing insights about the employees for making decisions, but on the flip side privacy of the employees will be affected as

		employees' data would not be confidential. Consent of the employees is essential to get insights about the employees else lots of risks will be there, thus the opportune use of HRA is essential.
2021	BatuolRamziAliAlsuliman(Etd)	Human Resource Analytics increases the competency level of the employees, for systematic utilization of human resource analysts, professionals must know about technology and data.

Theoretical framework.

The integration of HRA into organizational processes has readjusted the strategic part of hr. This study investigates how 2 core HRA factors, performance appraisal, rewards and recognition, affect performance management, intending to adopt HRA grounded on the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) and strategic decision making as intercessors.

The frame is predicated on human capital theory(Becker 1964), the resource grounded view RBV(Barney 1991), and utaut(Venkatesh et.al 2003), furnishing a comprehensive explanation of the connection between the constructs.

HRA refers to the methodical collection, analysis, and operation of hr related data to enhance decision-making and organizational performance (Marler and Boudreau 2017). By using analytics, Hr moves from suspicion-grounded to substantiation-grounded decision(Angrave et al. 2016).

Performance appraisals are prone to subjectivity data Data-grounded appraisal systems offer non-stop objective performance shadowing(Denusi and Maurphy 2017)/HRA allows associations to decipher patterns, prognosticate performance pitfalls, and design personalized development strategies(Bondarouk and Brewster 2016). aligning appraisal with strategic objectives.

Rewards and Recognition, both financial and nonfinancial, play a vital part in motivating workers (Grawitch, Gottschalk, and Munz 2006). HRA helps identify the most effective price structure for driving productivity (Stoehmeier 2018)

This aligns with the expectation proposition, where workers are more engaged when they see a clear link between performance and price.

Intentions to adopt HRA (UTAUT theory), the UTAUT model (Venkatesh ETAL 2003) identifies performance expectations, effort expectation, social influence, and ease of use as crucial predictors of technology relinquishment. Hr intention to adopt HRA reflects directors' beliefs that analytics improve decision quality, effectiveness, and planning delicacy (Parry and Battista 2019). Without strong relinquishment intentions, the implicit benefits of analytics remain unrealized; therefore, intention to adopt HRA functions as a first middleman in the process.

SDM involves deliberate, long-term organizational choices grounded in accurate data (Eisenhardt and Zbaracki, 1992). HRA provides prophetic perceptivity, script analysis, and pool simulations that enhance decision delicacy (Fitz-enznad Mattox, 2014). In RBV terms, logical decision-making capabilities are rare non-substitutable coffees that strengthen competitive positioning (Huseild 2018). The Strategic decision-making team is the alternative middleman. Links HRA relinquishes the network to operate. The Strategic decision-making team is the alternative middleman. Links HRA relinquishes the network to perform operational issues.

Performance management

It is operationalized in this study through employees' productivity and employee engagement.

Employee productivity- it refers to the effectiveness with which workers achieve performance targets (Delany and Huseild 1996)

Employee engagement- it relates to workers' emotional, cognitive, and behavioural commitment to their places (Kahn, 1990)

HRA creates a feedback circle enabling non-stop monitoring of these issues and guiding HR interventions to optimise results (Cascio and Boundreau 2016)

Conceptual Framework.

- Independent variables- Performance appraisal, Rewards, and Recognition.

- Mediators-Intentions to adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making.
- Dependent variables-Performance management with KPIs, Employee Productivity, and Employee Engagement.

The conceptual framework aims to explore how human resource analytics influence the performance management of employees concerning chain hotels in Bangalore, with mediating variables as intentions to adopt HRA and strategic decision making, UTAUT theory, and analytics give details of hr functions help in measuring the performance of employees with the help of production and engagement of employees.

Independent variables.

Performance Appraisal, Rewards and Recognition constitute fundamental functions through which data can be generated for analytical purposes. Each function contains different quantifiable metrics which process inputs to the HRA system, the value of HRA is derived from leveraging such data to inform hr decision([Marker and Boundaries 2017](#))

Performance appraisal-It elaborates the structured assessment of the performance of employees against specified outcomes.

Rewards and recognition-It includes monetary and non-monetary rewards for appreciation.

Thus, both of these functions of hr have data that is being used for analytical purposes.

HRA factors-As [per Angrave et al. \(2016\)](#), organisations that develop analytics capability in hr can shift from reactive to proactive decision-making, thus creating strategic value. Hence, these hr functions create a structured data set that serves as raw material for analytics.HRA is a construct that is being used by the organisation to convert data into strategic decision-making.

Intentions to adopt HRA

Intention to adopt HRA has a significant mediating role, analytics techniques have been used by hr professionals for decision making, UTAUT theory being given by [Venkatesh in the year\(2003\)](#) It fills the gap between the availability of data and strategic decision-making.

It has 4 constructs

Performance Expectancy-The individual perceives that it helps to have better job performance in the environment of HRA, which enhances the competencies of hr functions.

Efforts Expectancy- It is believed that if tools of HRA are accessible, then they can be easily adopted.

Social Influence-The degree to which top executives, colleagues believe that HRA should be adopted, hence it motivated to use the system.

Facilitating Conditions-The extent to which specialised help for the use of the system, operation support increases the liability of exposing HRA.

Hence, it is very important to understand that adoption of HRA has an actual role because accessibility of data is only beneficial if the organisation has the willingness to use it for decision-making.

Strategic decision making-According to [Leicht Deobald et. al\(2019\)](#), data-informed decision-making in hr requires a shift in mindset from intuition-based judgment to evidence-based human resource management. It is the efficiency of hr management for the utilization of details of HRA in forming strategies and policies. It fills the gap between intentions to adopt HRA and performance management. SDM has a significant role in taking evidence-based hr decisions.

Performance Management-

The outcome of the model is performance management, which is assessed by 2 KPIs.

- Employees' Productivity-The Competence level of employees in achieving targets.
- Employee Engagement- The involvement of employees in the organisation.

Figure 3

Model UTAUT THEORY(Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology)

Source: Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, 2003

Research Methodology

- **Research Design**

The present study takes on a quantitative research design to study the role of HRA in enhancing the performance management of employees in chain hotels in Bangalore.

This research has independent variables, ie, Performance appraisal, Rewards and recognition, Intentions to adopt HRA, and Strategic decision-making as a mediator, and Performance management as dependent variables that will be measured by key performance indicators, Employee productivity, and Employee engagement.

It is descriptive as well as exploratory research, and constructs are formed from existing literature. Data will be collected from a structured questionnaire distributed to human resource managers as respondents of each chain hotel in Bangalore, it includes close-ended questions measured through five points Likert scale, cluster sampling will be followed to collect data, and collected data will, be analyzed by using regression analysis, structural equation model(SEM) model be used to test the hypothesis, demographic variables will be analyzed using ANOVA and correlation technique.

Research Design ensures a comprehensive assessment of how HRA tools and demographic contexts contribute to effective management.

- **Calculation of Sample Size**

Total Population N= 140 (<https://nidhi.tourism.gov.in>)

Step 1: Initial sample size (n_0) using Cochran's formula:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2}$$

Substitute the given values:

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{3.8416 \cdot 0.25}{0.0025} = 384.16$$

So, the initial sample size (n_0) is **384.16**.

Step 2: Adjust for finite population (140)

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0 - 1}{N}}$$

Where:

- N = population size = 140
- n_0 = 384 (from above)

$$n = \frac{384}{1 + \frac{383}{140}} = \frac{384}{1 + 2.7357} = \frac{384}{3.7357} \approx 102.86$$

Calculation of the Sample Method.

The cluster sampling method is used in this study because each chain is one cluster. For example, Taj is one cluster having 9 properties throughout Karnataka, so we will take samples from 1 or 2 properties of Taj from one cluster of Taj.

- **Data Collection:**

Primary Data is collected using a structured questionnaire by human resource managers of chain hotels located in Karnataka, and secondary data is collected from journals and other publications.

- **Statistical tools:**

SPSS software will be used to perform statistical tests and to obtain accurate results. Reliability (Cronbach`s Alpha), Skewness, and Kurtosis tests will be done to measure the normality and abnormality of data. Regression analysis will also be done to analyze the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

4.0 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 3.0 Demographic Profile:

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	74	72.0
	Female	29	28.0

Figure 2

Description: Employee respondents were classified based on gender. Almost 72 per cent of respondents belong to the male category, and 28 per cent of respondents belong to the female category.

Table 3.1 Age

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age	25 - 35	15	14.6

	36 - 46	35	34.0
	47 -57	33	32.0
	58 -68	20	19.4

Figure 2.1

Description: The Majority of the respondents belonged to the age group of ranging between 25 and 35 years (14.6%), followed by respondents with an age of 36 – 46 years (34.0%). 47-57 years(32%) 58-68 years(19.4 %)

Table 3.2 Education

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Education	Under Graduate	30	29.1
	Post Graduate	58	56.3
	Phd.	5	4.9
	Others	10	9.7

Figure 2.3

Description: The Majority of the respondents have educational qualifications as post-graduates (56.3%), and 29.1% of respondents have undergraduate qualifications phd(4.9 %), others(9.7%)

Table 3.3 Experience

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Experience	6 – 15 years	20	19.4
	16 -25 years	45	43.7
	26 -30	38	36.9

Figure 2.4

Description: The majority have experience between 6-15 years (19.4%). (43.7%) of the respondents have experience between 16-25 years, and 36.9% of the respondents have experience of 26-30 years.

Table 4: Number of Rooms

Number of Rooms	Frequency	Percent
Up to 50	6	5.8
51 – 100	19	18.4
101 – 200	41	39.8
Above 200	37	35.9

Figure 3

Description: . The study found that 39.80% of the hotels have between 101 – 200 rooms, and 35.9% of the hotels have more than 200 rooms. 18.40% of the hotels have between 51 – 100 rooms.

Table 5: Age of Hotel

Age of Hotel	Frequency	Percent
6 – 10 years	26	25.2
11 – 20 years	47	45.6

Above 20 years	30	29.1
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Figure 4

Description: For the age of the hotel, 45.60% of the hotels are 11 - 20 years old, and 29.10% of the hotels are above 20 years old. 25.20% of the hotels are aged between 6 – 10 years.

Descriptive Statistics:

The descriptive statistics of the variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Rewards & Recognition	2	5	3.77	0.64	-0.79	-0.07
Performance Appraisal	2	5	3.67	0.77	-0.38	-0.63
HR Analytics Factors	3	5	4.14	0.46	-0.40	-0.41
Intention to Adopt HRA	2	5	3.31	0.84	0.21	-1.04
Strategic Decision Making	3	5	3.87	0.48	-0.17	-0.25
Performance Management	3	5	4.00	0.42	-0.05	-0.51

This **descriptive statistics table** gives a **summary of responses** from people who took part in your study. It helps you understand:

The descriptive statistics provide an overview of the participants' perceptions regarding the key variables under study. Among all variables, *HRA Factors* (M = 4.14, SD = 0.46) and *Performance Management* (M = 4.00, SD = 0.42) received the highest mean scores, indicating that respondents generally agreed or strongly agreed with statements related to the effective use of HRA practices and performance management in their organizations. *Strategic Decision Making* also showed a relatively high mean (M = 3.87, SD = 0.48), suggesting that participants perceived strategic use of HR-related data positively.

Rewards and Recognition (M = 3.77, SD = 0.64) and *Performance Appraisal* (M = 3.67, SD = 0.77) also received favorable responses, though with slightly more variation in opinions. The variable *Intention to Adopt HRA* had the lowest mean (M = 3.31, SD = 0.84), indicating a more neutral or uncertain attitude among respondents toward adopting HRA tools in the future.

The skewness and kurtosis values for most variables were within acceptable ranges, showing that the data were approximately normally distributed the variables was evaluated using internal consistency measurement with Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

The table 5 shows that the Cronbach's alpha values for all the variables have exceeded minimal threshold value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2010), ensuring the instrument's reliability for measurements.

Table 7: Reliability Analysis

Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Rewards & Recognition	5	0.84
Performance Appraisal	5	0.82
Human Resource Factors	5	0.92
Intention to Adopt HRA	5	0.88
Strategic Decision Making	5	0.89
Performance Management	5	0.90

Table 5 shows that the Cronbach's alpha values for all the variables have exceeded the minimal threshold value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2010), ensuring the instrument's reliability for measurements.

Mediation Analysis

The study hypothesises that Intention to Adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making mediates the relationship between Human Resource Factors and Performance Management. Initially, the direct effect was analysed using Human Resource Factors as the independent variable and Performance Management as the dependent variable (Figure 1).

Figure 5: Direct Effect of Human Resource Factors on Performance Management

The result of the direct effect model shows that the path coefficient value was 0.4 and the model was significant (p<0.05).

Table 8: Direct Effect of KM Infrastructure on Organizational Performance

Dependent Variable		Predictor Variable	Beta Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p-value	Result
Performance Management	<---	Human Resource Factors	0.34	0.08	3.69	***	Significant

The study initially examined the **direct relationship** between HRA Factors and Performance Management without including mediating variables. As shown in **Figure 1**, this model was tested to determine whether HRA practices—such as recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, and rewards and recognition—directly influence the performance management of employees. The results presented in **Table 6** indicate that HRA Factors have a **positive and statistically significant effect** on Performance Management, with a **standardized beta coefficient of 0.34**, a **critical ratio (C.R.) of 3.69**, and a **p-value < 0.001**. This suggests that effective implementation of HRA practices contributes meaningfully to improving how employee performance is managed within organizations. The significance of the model (p < 0.05) supports the hypothesis that HRA practices are a key driver of performance-related outcomes even before accounting for potential mediators.

Indirect Effect of Human Resource Factors on Performance Management

Indirect effect was measured by introducing the mediating variables, namely, Intention to Adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making.

Figure 6 Indirect Effect of Intention to Adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making on the relationship between Human Resource Factors on Performance Management

Table 9: Indirect Effect of Intention to Adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making on the relationship between Human Resource Factors on Performance Management

Assessment of Structural Model

Dependent Variable		Predictor Variable	Beta Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p-value	Result
Intention to Adopt HRA	<---	Human Resource Factors	0.31	0.17	3.27	0.00	Significant
Strategic Decision Making	<---	Human Resource Factors	0.20	0.09	2.08	0.04	Significant
Performance Management	<---	Intention to Adopt HRA	0.22	0.05	2.30	0.02	Significant

Performance Management	<---	Strategic Decision Making	0.19	0.08	2.08	0.04	Significant
Performance Management	<---	Human Resource Factors	0.24	0.08	2.55	0.01	Significant

From Table 7, it is evident that the introduction of mediator variable (Intention to Adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making) has significantly impacted the relation between the predictor variable (Human Resource Factors) and the dependent variable (Performance Management). However, the path coefficient between Human Resource Factors on Performance Management has reduced from 0.34 to 0.24. Thus, the results of the mediation analysis indicate that “partial mediation” has been reported due to the mediating effect of the variable (Intention to Adopt HRA and Strategic Decision Making) on the relationship between Human Resource Factors and Performance Management.

Validation Of the Structural Equation Model

The findings of the path analysis illustrating the link between the Predictor Variable and the Dependent Variable are provided in Table ** and Figure 1.

Figure 7 SEM Analysis

Table 10: Standardised Regression Estimates

Dependent Variable		Predictor Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p-value
Human Resource Factors (HRF)	<---	Rewards & Recognition (RR)	0.30	0.07	3.23	0.00**
Human Resource Factors (HRF)	<---	Performance Appraisal (PA)	0.41	0.06	4.41	***
Intention to Adopt HRA (INT)	<---	Human Resource Factors (HRF)	0.30	0.17	3.27	0.00**
Strategic Decision Making (DM)	<---	Human Resource Factors (HRF)	0.19	0.09	2.08	0.04*
Performance Management (PM)	<---	Intention to Adopt HRA (INT)	0.22	0.05	2.30	0.02*
Performance Management (PM)	<---	Strategic Decision Making (DM)	0.19	0.08	2.08	0.04*
Performance Management (PM)	<---	Human Resource Factors (HRF)	0.23	0.08	2.55	0.01*

From the above table and figure, it is evident that the regression coefficients for the factors like Rewards & Recognition (RR) ($\beta=0.30$) and Performance Appraisal (PA) ($\beta=0.41$) have showed a positive and significant relationship with the Human Resource Factors (HRF). Human Resource Factors (HRF) has significant positive effect on both Intention to Adopt HRA (INT) ($\beta=0.30$) and Strategic Decision Making (DM) ($\beta=0.19$). All the predictors like Intention to Adopt HRA (INT) ($\beta=0.22$), Strategic Decision Making (DM) ($\beta=0.19$) and Human Resource Factors (HRF) ($\beta=0.23$) have significant positive effect on Performance Management (PM)

Table 9 presents the values of the goodness of fit indices for the proposed model. Goodness of fit assesses the adequacy of the model in relation to the observed data. The table clearly indicates that the fit indices values for the measurement model fall within the acceptable range. Consequently, it is concluded that the model may be regarded as a suitable match. The indices, including the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), and

Comparative Fit Index (CFI), exceeded the required threshold of 0.9, indicating a flawless model fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Daire et al., 2008; Hair et al., 2010). The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) was below the advised threshold of 0.09 (Hair et al., 2010), indicating that the model exhibits an excellent fit. The overall results for model fit indices and metrics produced in the research are deemed satisfactory. Therefore, it can be argued that the SEM model is well suited for measurements and deriving conclusions.

Table 11: Goodness of Fit Indices

Indices	Suggested value	Obtained Value
Chi-square value	-	25.44
DF	-	8
Chi-square value/DF (CMIN)	< 5.00 (Hair et al., 2010)	3.18
GFI	> 0.90 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.94
AGFI	> 0.90 (Hair et al. 2010)	0.92
NFI	> 0.90 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.96
CFI	> 0.90 (Daire et al., 2008)	0.96
RMR	< 0.08 (Hair et al. 2010)	0.052
RMSEA	< 0.09 (Hair et al. 2010)	0.063

To assess the overall fit of the structural equation model, multiple goodness-of-fit indices were evaluated, as presented in Table 9. The Chi-square value for the model was 25.44 with 8 degrees of freedom, yielding a normed chi-square (CMIN/DF) of 3.18, which falls within the acceptable range of less than 5.0 (Hair et al., 2010), indicating a reasonable model fit.

The absolute fit indices revealed a good model fit, with the Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) and the Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI) recorded at 0.94 and 0.92, respectively, both exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.90 (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Hair et al., 2010). Similarly, incremental fit indices, including the Normed Fit Index (NFI = 0.96) and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.96), also surpassed the 0.90 benchmark, suggesting that the model has a strong improvement over the null model (Daire et al., 2008).

Furthermore, the Root Mean Square Residual (RMR) value was 0.052, which is below the acceptable maximum of 0.08, indicating a low level of residuals. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) was 0.063, within the acceptable threshold of 0.09, confirming that the model provides a good approximation of the population data (Hair et al., 2010).

Overall, the goodness-of-fit indices confirm that the proposed structural model fits the data well, justifying the subsequent analysis of path coefficients and mediation effects.

Finding.

The study analysed the impact of HRA factors on the performance management of employees in chain hotels with the intention of adopting HRA and strategic decision-making as mediating variables. SEM is being used on the collected data from 103 HR managers. The demographic profile of respondents suggested that most of the HRA managers are post-graduate with considerable experience in work in chain hotels. As the respondents are highly qualified, they have a good understanding of analytics and technology.

The descriptive analysis emphasized that many HR professionals have started using HRA in chain hotels, hence data-driven decisions are being made. As there are high mean scores across the constructs of HRA, it demonstrates a powerful execution level, especially in areas such as performance appraisal and reward and recognition, where analysis is being made many times to monitor the performance of the employees. Reliability and validity evaluation confirm that all variables are statistically sound.

The intention to adopt HRA acts as a mediator between HRA factors and performance management. Organisations that have adopted HRA technology would convert their HR process more effectively to measure performance. Strategic decision-making also acts as a significant mediator that assists HR managers in making evidence-based decisions.

Hence, it says that hr professionals who have started using HRA with the goals of the organization improve the quality of decisions and also the performance efficiency. HRA is not only a tool but also a strategic creator that converts hr from an administrative function into evidence-based decision-making and a partner within the organization

Discussions.

The study verified that HRA factors Performance appraisal, rewards, and recognition, significantly increase performance management within the chain hotels. It says that data-centric HR practices lead to translucency and strategic planning of human capital rewards. Appraisal indicates that the strongest impact is recommending that an analytics-based approach is helpful for the organization to assess the performance of the employees, hence data-driven decision helps in enhancing engagement and production of employees. Intention to adopt HRA and strategy decision-making is the mediating variable between HRA factors and performance management. It says that organisation that are adopting HRA tools change their practice more effectively into performance measurable outcomes. Hence, it says that analytics supports HR decisions and is also among strategic choices for long-term organizational sustainability. The mediating variables indicate that when hr managers effectively use analytics for strategic planning, staffing strategy, and talent management, the organizational performance management becomes more powerful and goal-oriented.

Theoretical Implication

The study comes up by combining the UTAUT theory with HRA and performance management. It justifies the intention to adopt HRA as the mediating variable linking hr practice to strategic results, hence it enhances knowledge and technology that helps HR managers in making evidence-based decisions, which also helps in achieving outcomes of employees and goals of the organizations. It also makes hr professional decisions to use analytic tools that positively affect their work.

Managerial Implications

From a managerial point of view, the study comes up with valuable insights for HR professionals and hr managers so that the performance of employees increases through analytics. The results emphasize that investment in training employees to use analytics also helps in encouraging the adoption of HRA. Managers also make sure that a combination of HR insights into strategic decision-making strengthens the efficiency and also brings precision in appraisal and rewards system, hence the study highlights that there is a requirement for data data-based culture because decisions of HR are evidence-based rather than intuition, which ensures sustainable organizational performance.

Conclusions.

This study focuses on the mediating variable, ie, intentions to adopt HRA and strategic decision making, both have a significant role in the hotel industry. In the hotel industry, where human assets have a major role to play, employees are highly competent to adopt HRA practices. Rewards and recognition, and performance appraisal are the main components for HRA factors, and have a positive impact on the performance of employees in chain hotels.

SEM results say that HRA factors have direct and indirect impacts. Rewards and recognition, performance appraisal helps in the formation of HRA factors which positively influence performance management, mediator intention to adopt HRA, and strategic decision making, also establishes a relationship between HRA factors and performance management. Successful execution of HRA factors is assisted by motivating employees for HRA adoption and strategic decision-making processes, which have a significant impact on the performance management of employees.

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